

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF DELAMINATION BUCKLING AND GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

Buckling induced growth of delaminations has been tested for tension-compression ($R=-1$) fatigue loading. Via Moiré-technique the out-of-plane (i.e. buckling) deformation of the delaminated region has been measured. Using numerical post-processing techniques the size and the shape of the delamination can be determined from this measurement. The post-buckling state of the specimens has then been analyzed by two-dimensional (plate) and three-dimensional (layered 3D shell) finite element models. First comparisons between experiment and analysis indicate that a prediction of the growth rate of delaminations might be possible via simulation of the post-buckling behaviour and computation of the energy release rates along the delamination front.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination - the disbond of two adjacent fibre reinforced layers of a laminate - is a prevalent state of damage for fibre reinforced materials such as carbon fibre reinforced epoxy [1]. If a delamination caused by impact or even occurring during the manufacturing process exceeds a certain size, it will progressively grow under service load conditions. The resulting loss in strength and stiffness of the affected component may lead to structural failure at a load level which is significantly lower than the load for which the component has been designed. Using empirically determined safety factors will help to prevent failure, but for an optimal utilization of the potential offered by fibre reinforced material as well as for the determination of inspection intervals, it is essential to be able to predict delamination growth under cyclic loading.

In this investigation criteria based on fracture mechanics are used to describe the delamination failure. Propagation therefore is to be expected when a function of the mixed mode energy release rates G_I , G_{II} , G_{III} along the delamination front locally exceeds a certain value G_c . We suppose that G_c is a material property independent from geometry and stacking sequence, however, dependent on the ply orientation of the layers adjacent to the plane of delamination.

The goal of the investigations presented is to obtain information on the dependence of buckling induced delamination growth on the mixed mode energy release rates resulting from

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cyclic loading and to verify the approach considered.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Test specimens according to Fig. 1 have been cut from prefabricated plates made of prepreg material (T300/914C) with a stacking sequence of $[\pm 5/ + 45/ \pm 5/ - 45/0/ \pm 85/0/ - 45/ \mp 5/ + 45/ \mp 5]$. Artificial circular delaminations have been introduced at interface 2/3 during manufacturing by embedding a double foil of a $20 \mu\text{m}$ thick release film to simulate a pre-damaged structure. An antibuckling guide with rectangular windows on both sides of the specimen is clamped to the test specimen, suppressing its global buckling. Loading frequency is 10 Hz at $R=-1$ with stress maxima varying between $180 - 200 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for an initial delamination diameter of 20 mm and $220 - 240 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for an initial delamination diameter of 10 mm . These stress maxima have shown to yield stable delamination growth.

Figure 1: Test specimen: $[\pm 5/ + 45/ \pm 5/ - 45/0/ \pm 85/0/ - 45/ \mp 5/ + 45/ \mp 5]$
Circular delamination embedded between plies 2 and 3

The out-of-plane (i.e. buckling) deformations of the delaminated region have been measured via Moiré technique. An example, figured in gray levels of constant displacements, is shown in Fig. 2. Using numerical post-processing procedures, the size and shape of the delaminated sublaminates as well as the delamination front contour may be obtained from the information stored in the digitized pictures [2].

Figure 2: Post-buckling out-of-plane displacements by Moiré measurement

SIMULATION OF POST-BUCKLING BEHAVIOUR

In a preliminary study quadrilateral layered plate elements (with four nodes) which allow transverse first order shear deformation have been used to keep computing times low. The investigations during this phase of the project focussed on the boundary conditions to be applied along the modeled section of the specimen, the influence of the delamination size modeled and the global performance of the nonlinear FE-code used [3, 4]. Only the region inside the window of the antibuckling guide was modeled by two subplates with the nodes located at the plane of delamination over the entire region modeled. It was found that the boundary conditions applied to the edges of the region modeled have no significant influence on the computed deformations provided we focus our interest on the region of stable delamination growth (e.g. load levels $\sigma_x \approx 220 - 240 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for a starter delamination with 10 mm diameter). This has been checked by applying first a clamped and then a simply supported condition. The same holds for the value of the linear buckling load for sublaminates buckling [5].

In order to achieve correct results for mode separation when computing energy release rates the use of three-dimensional FE models is required. Models of the entire window section are necessary for accurately computing mixed mode energy release rates along the delamination front contours, even in the case of geometrically symmetric specimens due to the existence of $\pm \alpha$ plies. A newly developed *layered element with eight nodes* formulated according to a continuum based three-dimensional shell theory [6] has been used for the three-dimensional models of the specimens. This element has been employed in order to reduce computing time, to prevent the elements from locking for small element thickness to element length ratios and to assure complete compatibility with the contactor and target elements used to avoid structural overlapping in the vicinity of the crack front [7]. The top two $[\pm 5]$ layers of the sublaminates have been modeled by one element over the thickness of each layer. Also the $[+45]$ layer of the base laminate which is adjacent to the plane of delamination has been modeled by one element over the thickness. The remaining 13 layers of the base laminate have been joined in two elements of $[\pm 5 / - 45 / 0 / \pm 85]$ and $[0 / - 45 / \mp 5 / + 45 / \mp 5]$ layup respectively (see Fig. 3). A simply supported condition has been applied as boundary condition along the edges of the modeled section of the specimen representing the edges of the window of the antibuckling guide. As already mentioned above the boundary conditions chosen do not have a significant influence on the buckling behaviour of the sublaminates.

Figure 3: Post-buckling deformation (magnified)
 Delamination diameter 20 mm, compression loading $\sigma = 180 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2}$

Additional computations were performed using a specially developed *delamination process element* which is based on a simplified Reissner-Mindlin plate theory [8]. The results obtained using both element types for modeling a specimen with a circular delamination of 10 mm diameter are presented in Fig. 4. The corresponding load displacement values agree very well. Computations of the load displacement curves for a specimen with a delamination of 20 mm diameter yield the same behaviour as shown in Fig. 5. A picture of the post-buckling deformation of a specimen with 20 mm initial delamination is shown in Fig. 3 for an applied compression load $\sigma = 180.0 \text{ N/mm}^2$ which corresponds to the load level where stable delamination growth is observed in the experiment.

Figure 4: Computed load displacement behaviour Specimen containing a circular delamination of 10 mm diameter

Figure 5: Computed load displacement behaviour Specimen containing a circular delamination of 20 mm diameter

Comparing the computed displacements with those measured during a quasi-static test and during the first load cycle of the fatigue tests (Fig. 6 and 7) shows a large imperfection sensitivity of the buckling situation, especially for the specimen with the 10 mm initial delamination. Only if the diameter of the delamination is slightly increased (by an amount which is within the production tolerance of the specimens, i.e. 0.6 mm) and if the 40 μm thick double release foil used to create the artificial delamination is included in the model, the computed displacement values lie well within the scatter band of experiments.

Figure 6: Comparison of experimentally determined displacements with FE-results Specimen containing a circular delamination of 10 mm diameter

Figure 7: Comparison of experimentally determined displacements with FE-results Specimen containing a circular delamination of 20 mm diameter

PREDICTION OF DELAMINATION GROWTH

The most significant step for the current approach is the accurate computation of the distribution of the mixed mode energy release rates along arbitrarily shaped delamination fronts. It has been found that the virtual crack closure method is most favourable for this purpose because the separation of the total energy release rate into the contributions by the different crack opening modes is possible in a straight forward manner [9]. When using this method only one FE-computation is necessary for a given delamination front which is beneficial especially when solving large geometrically non-linear problems. Preliminary investigations employing DCB and ENF specimens assured the reliability of the techniques used for computation of energy release rate distributions along straight and curved delamination fronts [10]. In addition, convergence studies for ENF and SLB specimens [11] did not show the non-convergence of the virtual crack closure method associated with the oscillatory singularity as reported in the literature, e. g. in [12, 13]. This may be due to very small bimaterial constants of the considered interfaces [14] or due to finite element meshes that are in the range of relatively constant results for G_I, G_{II} and G_{III} [13]. The issue will be investigated further.

Computed mixed mode energy release rates for the specimen with a circular starter delamination of 10 mm as obtained for the maximum compression load of the experimental load cycle are shown in Fig. 8. The computed energy release rates in the phase of tension loading are negligible which confirms previous assumptions that delamination growth occurs in the compression phase of the test only.

Figure 8: Distribution of energy release rates along delamination front
Specimen containing a circular delamination of 10 mm diameter

Looking at the distribution of the energy release rates we expect the delamination to start growing into load direction, slightly off 0° and 180° (i.e. following the [-5] layer) which is in excellent agreement with experimental results (see Fig. 9). The initial growth should be confined to the regions $-45^\circ \leq \phi \leq +45^\circ$ and $-135^\circ \leq \phi \leq +225^\circ$ because outside of these regions the total energy release rate is smaller than the threshold values for delamination growth in mode I (G_{Ith}) and mode II (G_{IIth}). This also agrees with the experiment. A first prediction of the initial growth rate based on Paris Law parameters for a 0°/0°-interface

from [15] and comparison with measurement (see Fig. 9) shows that a prediction of buckling induced delamination growth by the considered approach might be possible.

Figure 9: X-ray photograph of a growing delamination
Comparison of prediction with measurement

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